

NEWSERA - Citizen Science as the
new paradigm for Science
Communication

Deliverable 6.1

Events 1

Revision: v1.0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 87312

DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Due date: March 31th, 2020

Actual submission date: April 1st, 2020

Project start date: January 1st, 2020

Duration: 36 months

Work Package concerned: WP6

Concerned work package leader: Formicablu

Dissemination level:

PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Cl: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Authors:

Lisa Lazzarato (Formicablu)

Oriol Agulló, Rosa Arias (Science for Change)

Revision history:

revision	date	Contributor	Description
v1.0	17.03.2020	Lisa Lazzarato (Formicablu)	First Draft
v1.0	01.04.2020	Oriol Agulló, Rosa Arias (Science for Change)	Final Version

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise

Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

SUMMARY

NEWSERA will analyse and evaluate the complex and multidirectional science communication strategies, including digital and non-digital ones, addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders in citizen science projects across Europe as the new paradigm for science communication.

The overall aim of NEWSERA is to demonstrate the virtues of citizen science as an inclusive, broad and powerful science communication mechanism that can allow to increase trust in science communication and, in turn, in science at large, while opening up science and innovation to society, raising awareness and educating in science, and reducing the chances of incurring in fake news by promoting critical thinking.

This document presents the events attended and planned by the NEWSERA consortium to promote, disseminate and actively engage the project with different audiences **during its first year of activity.**

NEWSERA project is focused on four target audiences, which correspond to the stakeholders represented by the **quadruple helix model**¹ - civil society, industry and SMEs, the scientific community, and the policy makers. NEWSERA is taking specially into account the **citizen science practitioners** and **data journalists** according to the aim of implementation of concepts Citizen Science Communication and Journalism.

Events are a crucial component of the NEWSERA project, specially regarding the **#CitSciComm labs** to be launched. They will be conceived as **co-creation spaces** to understand how science is being communicated in citizen science projects, identify opportunities and challenges, and co-design innovative communication strategies with several expert communities.

Following this co-creation spirit, the **NEWSERA kickoff meeting** (Barcelona, 4-6 February 2020) blended a consortium formal meeting to launch the project with the consortium partners and our Project Officer, together with two days of participatory workshops that simulate the functioning of the future NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs. For the co-creation sessions, local experts, including citizen science practitioners, science communicators and data journalists, were invited in order to look together for better and effective communication strategies addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders.

¹ Cavallini S., Soldi R., Friedl J., Volpe M. *Using the quadruple helix approach to accelerate the transfer of Research and Innovation Results to Regional Growth*. European Union, 2016. [doi: 10.2863/408040](https://doi.org/10.2863/408040)

The aim of the co-creation sessions was to define common communication challenges in citizen science projects, to identify appropriate communication strategies for each stakeholder group, and to define the general lines of the #CitSciComm Labs envisaged by NEWSERA. For the first time, the two communities started a common dialogue that helped identify common opportunities and challenges.

Regarding the events, meetings and #CitSciComm Labs co-creation sessions to come that were planned for 2020, the COVID-19 crisis poses a high degree of uncertainty in the project. Following the indications from the European Commission, all travels will be cancelled or postponed at least until the end of June. For the planned events, Consortium meetings and #CitSciComm Labs sessions planned, the Consortium will decide on a case by case basis whether to postpone them, make them virtual, or change the scope and decentralize them to a local level. On the other hand, the Consortium will be attentive to the new dates of external events, such as scientific conferences, related to NEWSERA that have been postponed because of the COVID-19 crisis.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Kick-off meeting in Barcelona (M2)	6
1.1 Formal Kick-off meeting	6
1.2 Co-creation Lab testing in Barcelona	11
1.2.1 Day 1: Simulation of #CitSciComm Labs addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders	12
Co-creation methodology: the 35 game	13
Co-creation methodology: Find your pilot!	15
Co-creation methodology: Empathy map	17
Co-creation methodology: Elevator pitch	20
Results of the co-creation sessions during Day 1	21
1.2.2 Day 2: Simulation of #CitSciComm Labs addressed to science communicators and data journalists	23
Work Group 1: the challenges!	24
Work Group 2: mixed groups	26
Summary of methodology contributions during co-creation sessions	26
1.3 Kick-off meeting press clipping	28
2. Planned events (M3 - M12)	29
2.1 NEWSERA Consortium Meetings	29
2.2 #CitSciComm Labs sessions	30
2.3 External events	32

1. Kick-off meeting in Barcelona (M2)

Description and details of the contents of the formal kick-off meeting and the two days of co-creation sessions that took place with external guests in Barcelona (4-6 February 2020).

1.1 Formal Kick-off meeting

The consortium held its kick-off meeting on **February 4-6, 2020** at CosmoCaixa Science Museum in Barcelona. It included a first day for the formal meeting between partners and two days devoted to co-creation workshops with external guests to simulate the functioning of the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs. All partners were present, a total of 16 people.

The following list shows the consortium members and the representatives from the European Commission and the Research Executive Agency that attended and contributed with a presentation during the formal meeting.

nº	Name	Surname	Institution
1	Rosa	Arias	Science for Change
2	Oriol	Agulló	Science for Change
3	Elisabetta	Tola	Formicablu
4	Lisa	Lazzarato	Formicablu
5	Marco	Boscolo	Formicablu
6	Francesca	Conti	Formicablu
7	Marzia	Mazzonetto	Formicablu
8	Anna	Violato	Formicablu
9	Francisco	Sanz	Ibercivis
10	Maite	Pelacho	Ibercivis
11	Cristina	Luís	FC.ID
12	Izaskun	Lacunza	FECYT
13	Ana	Elorza	FECYT
14	Federico	Neresini	UNIPD
15	Paolo	Giardullo	UNIPD
16	Raluca	Iagher	Research Executive Agency

Table 1. List of NEWSERA consortium members and our Project Officer that attend the KoM in Barcelona

The full agenda of the formal NEWSERA kick-off meeting was:

09:30	10:00	Registration
10:00	10:20	Presentation “Citizen Science as the new paradigm for Science Communication” , Rosa Arias, Oriol Agulló, SfC
10:20	10:40	Presentation about policy perspectives Ms. Aleksandra Hebda, Policy Officer, EC
10:40	11:00	Presentation by NEWSERA Project Officer Ms. Raluca Iagher, Project officer, REA
11:00	11:30	Networking coffee break game: <i>Fake or real news?</i>
11:30	12:15	Presentations to introduce the project partners. Previous experience together and main contributions to NEWSERA
12:15	13:00	WP1 & WP8: Project management (tasks & deliverables, meetings, internal communication, project templates) and Ethics requirements, Rosa Arias, SfC
13:00	13:30	WP2: Analysis of Citizen Science as a Science Communication Tool, Paolo Giardullo, UNIPD
13:30	14:30	Lunch break & Networking
14:30	15:00	WP3: Co-design of innovative strategies in Citizen Science Communication, Izaskun Lacunza, FECYT
15:00	15:30	WP4: The NEWSERA Pilots Implementing the concepts of Citizen Science Communication and Citizen Science Journalism, Rosa Arias, SfC
15:30	15:50	WP5: Evaluation and impact assessment. The legacy of NEWSERA, Cristina Luis, FC.ID
15:50	16:00	Kampal , Francisco Sanz, IBERCIVIS
16:00	16:30	WP6: Dissemination and Communication Actions, Elisabetta Tola, FORMICABLU
16:30	17:00	WP7: Ethics and Data Protection strategies in NEWSERA, Francisco Sanz, IBERCIVIS
17:00	17:30	Co-design of dynamics for the co-creation workshops, All Partners & PO
17:30	17:45	Remarks and conclusions, Rosa Arias, SfC
17:45	18:00	Plan & End of Meeting

Table 2. Agenda of the first day of the NEWSERA KoM: “The formal meeting”

The **Project Officer** from the Research Executive Agency, **Ms. Raluca Iagher**, gave insights on the management of H2020 projects. The Science with and for Society specific call of Horizon 2020 in particular was presented, its strategic lines, sister projects, and the results of the interim evaluation. Some anticipations were also given on the new research program Horizon Europe (2021-2027).

Aleksandra Hebda, from the Open Science Unit, DG Research & Innovation of the European Commission, attended remotely and presented the policy perspective.

Picture 1. Whole NEWSERA Consortium listening to the Aleksandra Hebda online presentation about Policy Perspective.

Then the meeting proceeded with presentations of the partners and their work packages activities. The activity of the first months was planned and some decisions were taken regarding visual identity and social strategy, as well as the research to be initiated within WP2. Collaboration and joint actions to be undertaken with other similar research projects (sister SwafS-19 projects) were also addressed.

Here are some pictures of the discussions held during the formal kick-off meeting.

Picture 2. Rosa Arias and Oriol Agulló, Science for Change, making the introduction to the Kick-off meeting to Consortium members

Picture 3. Francisco Sanz, Ibercivis, explaining the Kampal tool, to be used to evaluate the impact of communication strategies in WP5

Picture 4. Elisabetta Tola, from Formicablu, introducing the discussion about communication strategies in order to explain WP6

The main decisions that were made during the formal KoM are:

- Request for a common meeting with the sister projects funded by SwafS-19 to establish common communication strategies, allow for mutual learning, and perhaps organize common actions and events.
- Move the next consortium meeting, in Padova, from November to the second week of December because of the partners availability.
- Keep the online monthly meetings of the Executive Board every first Thursday each month timing 11.30h CET, to be held through BlueJeans.
- Create two working groups to decide the strategy to collect information from citizen science projects, in the framework of WP2.
- Organize a virtual call to determine and set the optimum #CitSciComm Labs composition, to allow for having more science communicators and data journalists to support the citizen science practitioners, as well as potentially having more than one citizen science project participating per lab, as was originally foreseen.
- We decided on a logo proposal and discussed the best communication strategy (less NEWSERA channels, but greater use of the hashtag #NEWSERA through the social network and existing channels of the partners, thus getting to wider and already established audiences, so as to increase the outreach and the project impact).

1.2 Co-creation Lab testing in Barcelona

The NEWSERA Kick-off meeting included two co-creation sessions with external stakeholders, which took place on February 5 and 6 2020, at the same venue. The second and third days were conceived as a testing experience, simulating the setting up and working of the #CitSciComm Labs, which will be realized during the project.

- **Day 1.** #CitSciComm Labs addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders
- **Day 2.** Cross-cutting #CitSciComm Lab addressed to science communicators and data journalists to establish dialogues and support the CS community

External guests, being local representatives of citizen science projects, science communicators and data journalists, were invited. A total of 17 people attended in total:

nº	Name	Surname	Institution	Expertise
1	Sonia	Garcinuño	“la Caixa” Banking Foundation	Science communication
2	Alba	García	I2Cat	Citizen science
3	Sílvia	Bravo	Freelance	Science communication
4	Xavier	Basagaña	ISGlobal	Citizen science
5	Diana	Reinoso	SfC	Citizen science
6	Silvina	Frucella	Airenet	Citizen science
7	Federica	Beduini	ICFO	Science communication
8	Pau	Fortuño	FEHM-Lab Research Group UB	Citizen science
9	Montse	Llasat-Botija	GAMA-UB	Citizen Science
10	Raül	Toran	ISGlobal / ACCC	Science communication
11	Michele	Catanzaro	Freelance	Science communication
12	Joan	Mendoza	UB	Citizen science
13	Jordi	Díaz-Marcos	CCiTUB	Science communication
14	Cristina	Junyent	Ciència en societat	Science communication
15	Karma	Peiró	Freelance	Data journalism
16	Victòria	Oliveres	Freelance	Data journalism
17	Salvador	Ferré	Eduscopi	Science communication

Table 3. List of external participants attendance to the co-creation sessions held during the KoM of NEWSERA

The results of the two co-creation days have been compiled in a spark (<https://spark.adobe.com/page/hJM6Vy23lvXMJ/>) and are shown in the next sections of this deliverable.

1.2.1 Day 1: Simulation of #CitSciComm Labs addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders

The aim of the first co-creation day was to develop a simulation of operation of the four #CitSciComm Labs addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders.

The planned agenda for the first day was:

February 5, 2020

09:30 - 10:00	Registration and welcome, SfC
10:00 - 10:30	Presentation of NEWSERA to external participants, SfC
10:30 - 11:00	Pechakucha by external participants: 20 slides 20 sec. per slide
11:00 - 11:30	Networking coffee break game
11:30 - 13:00	Co-creating challenges: The 35 game!
13:00 - 13:30	Find your pilot game!
13:30 - 14:30	Lunch break & Networking
14:30 - 15:45	Defining your stakeholders with your empathy map
15:45 - 17:15	Co-designing innovative engaging strategies
17:15 - 17:30	Remarks and conclusions
17:30 - 17:45	Plan & End of meeting

Table 4. Agenda of second day of Barcelona KoM

List of external participants during the first day:

nº	Name	Surname	Institution	Expertise
1	Diana	Reinoso	SfC	Citizen science
2	Silvina	Frucella	Airenet	Citizen science
3	Federica	Beduini	ICFO	Science communication
4	Pau	Fortuño	FEHM-Lab Research Group UB	Citizen science
5	Montse	Llasat-Botija	GAMA-UB	Citizen Science
6	Raül	Toran	ISGlobal	Science communication
7	Joan	Mendoza	UB	Citizen science
8	Jordi	Díaz-Marcos	CCiTUB	Science communication
9	Cristina	Junyent	Ciència en societat	Science communication
10	Victòria	Oliveres	Freelance	Data journalism
11	Salvador	Ferré	Eduscopi	Science communication

Table 5. List of external participants attendance in second day of Barcelona KoM

First each NEWSERA consortium member presented itself explaining the expertise and role in the project. Afterwards the external participants also introduced themselves. This was followed by presentations from each external participant, mainly representing citizen science projects currently under execution in the Barcelona area, including: Ciència en societat, Cities-Health, NightUp, ACCC, RiuNet and Nanoeduca.

Co-creation methodology: the 35 game

The first group dynamics was to identify the **main challenges faced in the communication of citizen science projects with different stakeholder groups**. To do this, we played a dynamic named **35 game**. Participants had to choose individually what main challenges they are facing in the communication of citizen science projects and share them with another participant, so as to distribute 7 evaluation points between the 2 challenges identified. The exercise was repeated 5 times and then the main challenges were ranked according to the agreed votes.

The resulting common challenges identified were:

1. **Sustained engagement:** How to make participants in CS projects feel valuable and useful after contributing the first time and motivate them enough to keep contributing? How to be inclusive?
2. **Reliability of citizen generated data:** How to increase the trust of traditional scientists in citizen generated data? How to demonstrate the impact? How can CS achieve recognition as a methodology from the scientific community?
3. **Engaging the “non-usual suspects”:** How can CS projects reach non usual audiences and underrepresented groups? How can we involve more people? How do we find their motivation for engagement?
4. **Simplifying the scientific message to reach the communities:** How can we keep the level of excellence and complexity and communicate the message to society? How can we find the balance while making the message accessible?
5. **Other challenges:** Don't scare citizens! Awareness raising. Address ethical issues with data collection. Facilitate data collection. Think of incentive mechanisms. Funding. Demonstrate the potential of CS projects to inform policies.

Pictures 5, 6, 7, 8 & 9. Final composition of the main challenges identified by internal and external participants.

Co-creation methodology: Find your pilot!

Per each challenge identified, participants were divided by groups to think how a certain stakeholder group could help overcoming the challenge. In addition, citizen science practitioners selected the challenges faced by their projects.

Biggest challenge in communication (in CS projects)?	How can this stakeholder group help you?				CS Projects facing this challenge
	Civil Society	Policy Makers	Industry & SMEs	Career Scientist	
1) How to keep the engagement of participants in CS projects to keep contributing? How to do it in an inclusive way?	Showing their needs through platforms, civil organizations, focus groups and asking for improvements ; participating and connecting with other knowledge groups	Making needed investments and adding in their agendas citizen concerns	Citizens concerns must be a priority to include in their corporate social responsibility strategy		Floodup, D-NOSES, NightUp, Cities-Health, Biodiversity 4all, Invasoras.pt
2) How to increase the recognition of CS by the scientific community?		A real application of CS projects in policy making can convince the scientific community	Industry examples of "Beta testers" with CS	Define "standards" to "certify" each CS project. Use examples of old "citizen science" (e.g. meteorological volunteers)	Riunet, Bioblitz, Lichens of Bcn, Biodiversity 4all
3) How to reach underrepresented groups and to involve more people than those already participating in CS projects?	Journalists, youtubers, influencers, citizen networks	Local authorities endorsement	Netflix series	Show how science impacts daily life. Reveal the secrets behind common things	FloodUp, Biodiversity 4all, NightUp, D-NOSES, Invasion.pt, Cities-Health
4) Need to simplify the scientific message to reach the communities	Identify the real value to society and give feedback. Train citizen scientists how to do that	funding, social communication, make the project relevant and visible	Explain the complexity of the subjects. Collaborate with outcomes	Social scientists. Methodology: pre-tests, feedback, etc.	Cities-Health, Inputmain, Vigilantes del aire
5) Don't scare citizens; issues	Partner with hackers, ask	Funding. More info to	Better communication	Share results	Riunet, Bioblitz,

with sharing data; make people more aware; facilitate data collection; incentives

people what is scary for them

citizens. Sell the project benefits to policy makers. Align agendas

on and less marketing. Open up data

Lichens of Bcn, D-NOSES, European datajournalism EU

Table 6. List of stakeholders and CS projects related to the main challenges identified

How can this stakeholder group help you?

Civil Society: showing their needs through platforms, civil organizations, focus groups and asking for improvements; participating and connecting with other knowledge groups

Policy makers: making needed investments and adding in their agendas citizen concerns

Industry & SMEs: citizens concerns must be a priority to include in their corporate social responsibility strategy

Potencial CS Projects facing this challenge: Floodup, D-NOSES, NightUp,

Picture 10. Outcomes for the first main challenge proposed available for external participants through [Adobe Spark](#).

Once the results were shared by the different groups, a voting round was made in order to select the citizen science projects within the room that will act as “pilots” to work in an innovative communication strategy addressed to a specific stakeholder group in the next co-creation sessions. The project selected were:

- #CitSciComm Lab addressed to civil society: [NightUp](#)
- #CitSciComm Lab addressed to policy makers: [D-NOSES](#)
- #CitSciComm Lab addressed to industry & SMEs: [RiuNet](#)
- #CitSciComm Lab addressed to career scientists: [Vigilantes del Aire](#)

Co-creation methodology: Empathy map

In groups, and for the different Citizen Science projects selected and the corresponding stakeholder group, empathy maps were built to put ourselves in the shoes of the stakeholder and understand their communication needs.

	Civil Society	Policy Makers	Industry & SMEs	Career Scientists
Pilot Project	NightUp	D-NOSES	RiuNet	Vigilantes del aire
Think and feel	<p>Light is necessary. Why should we change it? I didn't know it was such an important issue</p> <p>Supernice project since it addresses an everyday life issue</p> <p>I didn't know if light pollution affects living beings</p> <p>I can contribute (in an easy form) to increase information about lights</p>	<p>To reveal that there is an odor problem in my city</p> <p>These people are going to do the project anyway, so I'm going to be proactive</p> <p>What is this tale about citizen science?</p> <p>Why do I need to address odour pollution?</p>	<p>I will improve my image and relationship with the community (CSR)</p> <p>I will publicly show my own impact</p> <p>It is a new and strange subject</p> <p>It has the risk of finding unpleasant results for which I will be responsible</p>	<p>It could be or not scientifically valid but probably the effort is worth it (and not too costly)</p> <p>They are upset people from CS calling "science" to this type of initiatives (not everything is science)</p> <p>Another one of those things of relations with society</p> <p>Waste of time</p>
Hear	<p>It affects animals</p> <p>I will hear less insects?</p> <p>More light = more noise... will be this project useful for decreasing the noise</p> <p>Darkness correlates with crime</p> <p>I will hear that light pollution is not that important as urban security</p> <p>Led are better than conventional lamps</p>	<p>Press, media, citizens complaints</p> <p>I've got the Airennet people complaining, I could use the opportunity...</p>	<p>The environmentalists are going to criticize me</p> <p>Industry pollutes</p> <p>Some other companies are already involved</p>	<p>The scientific community distributing strawberries...</p> <p>It is a project already carried out without citizen participation, so the scientific methodology already exists</p>
See	<p>I see colours of lights</p> <p>Changing while running</p> <p>I will see more lights and their colours</p> <p>I can't see the stars</p> <p>My neighbour has intrusive lights</p> <p>Lack of street lights</p> <p>I need really heavy curtains to not see light from the street</p>	<p>This has been a problem for years... I know no one has complained, I can ignore the problem</p> <p>Industry is aware of the project but not willing to do anything about it</p>	<p>I'm going to lose production time</p> <p>How much money is it going to cost me?</p>	<p>They see strawberries being distributed</p> <p>Potential of society engagement</p> <p>The project is replicable and scalable</p> <p>There is a good citizen response</p> <p>Many people involved</p>

<p>Say and do</p>	<p>Have you ever been aware of the light's colour? Have a look at the lights of your neighborhood What you see Take photos at night! Anonymously?</p>	<p>I can make a pilot project</p>	<p>I'm going to take the environmental responsibility label It is an opportunity to make production processes more efficient and educate employees</p>	<p>Complaint Here they are again wasting money on useless things. Buying strawberries?</p>
<p>Pain</p>	<p>Will it work with my device? Sharing Position issues Making photos at night? Use of data connection Should I consider myself as responsible for loss of biodiversity just because of lights in my garden?</p>	<p>Complaints = less votes Image of city It's gonna get me in trouble with the industry</p>	<p>Rising production costs</p>	<p>They are worried about the validity of data because maybe citizens don't take care enough Data reliability Time spent</p>
<p>Gain</p>	<p>Efficiency of lightbulbs What is the benefit for my health? Less light pollution Less light... less cars? Contributions to urban governance Correction of the problem</p>	<p>I must defend the welfare of the people If I show myself as a leader, I win over the citizens I can be a success story and improve my political standing (position as pioneer)</p>	<p>Generate environmental culture within companies improve the environment, enhancing the company's image and increasing its value</p>	<p>It seems that they are going to gain a high number of data Maybe would be useful for enhancing students inscriptions to scientific facilities Useful for research People know how research works Visibility of the research groups</p>

Table 7. Outcomes from empathy map exercise from each group

Picture 11. Participants contributing to one of the empathy maps created during the co-creation labs in Barcelona.

Think and feel: Light is necessary. Why should we change it? I didn't know it was such an important issue. I didn't know light pollution affects living beings.

Hear: It affects animals. I will hear less insects? More light = more noise... will be this project useful for decrease the noise. Darkness correlates with crime. I will hear that light pollution is not that important as urban security. Led are better than conventional lamps

See: I see colours of lights. I can't see the stars. Lack of street lights

Say and do: Have you ever been aware of the light's colour. Take photos at night!

Picture 12. Example of empathy map available for external participants included in Adobe Spark.

Co-creation methodology: Elevator pitch

The last dynamic of the first day was an elevator pitch of the innovative communication strategy defined for the pilot projects and the corresponding stakeholder group. This dynamic consisted in prototyping a science communication strategy in a collaborative way with the members of each group. To do so, each person thought of a strategy, without saying anything, shared it with another member of the group who added comments, and at the end of the round, all the strategies were read and the most appropriate one was decided. Then, the winner of the group pitched the idea to the rest of the groups, with an **outcome of four innovative communication strategies addressed to a specific stakeholder group** for the citizen science projects selected as pilots.

Type of stakeholder	Civil Society	Policy Makers	Industry & SMEs	Career Scientists
Pilot Project	NightUp	D-NOSES	RiuNet	Vigilantes del aire
Claim	Catch the light	You are what you smell!	Making industry a positive actor	Strawberries fields forever
Short Description	Night walks to photograph the different colours of the night lighting	Call for citizens to bring flower pots in front of the town hall	Mobilize and organize citizens to put the river in the public discourse, through a social media campaign (using the app)	Distribute strawberries among communities of scientists explaining the project and publicizing its results
Objectives	Raise awareness of light pollution	Raise awareness Giving visibility Increase OdourCollect followers and app users	To convince companies to join the RiuNet citizen science project and improve their industrial processes, then communicate the effect in water quality or quantity (and assess the changes with RiuNet)	Publicize the project Make your results relevant to the scientific community
Testing Procedures	Organize a contest with the best night photographs taken by users	Somewhere meaningful where the press can go Social media strategy One-day action Choose a meaningful day	Organizing activities in civic centres, etc. Then, convince companies about using citizen science in a positive way	Start handing out strawberries and explaining the project in front of hundreds of researchers

Table 8. Outcomes of the innovative communication strategies defined for each citizen science project and each stakeholder group

**Civil Society-
NightUp**

Claim
Catch the light

Short description
Night walks to photograph the different colours of the night lighting

Objectives
Raise awareness of light pollution

Testing Procedures
Organize a contest with the best night photographs taken by users

Picture 13. Example of one science communication strategy collected at Adobe Spark: <https://spark.adobe.com/page/hJM6Vy23lvXMJ/>

Pictures 14. Groups from elevator pitch methodology discussing their science communication strategies.

Results of the co-creation sessions during Day 1

The aim of the co-creation sessions during Day 1 was to simulate the future work that can be done in the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders, where science communication experts and data journalists will be helping citizen science practitioners to communicate more and better with their selected audiences, thus increasing their project outreach. The co-creation exercises were conceived as a whole, first to identify common communication challenges in citizen science projects, to later select some of the projects as examples and work on communication strategies to talk with a specific stakeholder group. The results obtained are shown in Table 8.

In relation to the methodology used, some general considerations to take into account when running co-creation workshops are:

- It is important to generate spaces of individual proposal and exchange of opinions, so as to generate an active attitude amongst the participants
- Promoting prioritization and consensus helps feeling part of the same process
- Going from the most general to the most concrete helps connecting participants with practical issues and generates debate
- Thinking empathetically on the impact of the actions helps validating the proposed actions and their potential interest
- Ending by generating a proposal helps to validate the collective process

The experience was highly satisfactory to all participants, who, as a result, wanted to get involved in the NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs, since they saw the value of the exercise. The Consortium was also really satisfied as these are very good news for NEWSERA future work!

1.2.2 Day 2: Simulation of #CitSciComm Labs addressed to science communicators and data journalists

The aim of the second day was to simulate the functioning of the #CitSciComm Lab addressed to science communicators and data journalists to put them in contact with citizen science practitioners and identify common opportunities and challenges.

The planned agenda for the second day was:

February 6, 2020

09:30	-	09:45	Registration and welcome, SfC
9:45	-	10:15	Presentation of NEWSERA to external participants, SfC
10:15	-	10:30	Brief introduction to data journalism, Formicablu
10:30	-	11:30	Work group 1: the challenges! Journalists: Which is the main challenge that you face when you are working with (citizen generated) data? Citizen science practitioners: How do we use citizen generated data to produce attractive stories for journalists?
11:30	-	12:00	Networking coffee break
12:00	-	12:15	Sharing of Work Group 1 outcomes
12:15	-	13:15	Work group 2: mixed groups (Journalists + CS practitioners) Finding the common ground!
13:15	-	13:30	Sharing of Work Group 2 outcomes
13:30	-	13:45	Conclusion & Follow up & End of meeting
13:45	-	15:00	Optional: lunch & networking

Table 9. Agenda of third day of Barcelona KoM

List of external participants of the second day:

nº	Name	Surname	Institution	Expertise
1	Sonia	Garcinuño	“la Caixa” Banking Foundation	Science communication
2	Alba	García	I2Cat	Citizen science
3	Sílvia	Bravo	Freelance	Science communication
4	Xavier	Basagaña	ISGlobal	Citizen science
5	Diana	Reinoso	SfC	Citizen science
6	Silvina	Frucella	Airenet	Citizen science
7	Federica	Beduini	ICFO	Science communication
8	Michele	Catanzaro	Freelance	Science communication
9	Karma	Peiró	Freelance	Data journalism
10	Victòria	Oliveres	Freelance	Data journalism

Table 10. List of external participants attendance in third day of Barcelona KoM

Work Group 1: the challenges!

We made two working groups, the first one with data journalists and science communicators and the second one with citizen science practitioners. We asked them about:

Citizen Science practitioners group: How do we use citizen generated data to produce attractive stories for journalists?

Challenges: Transmission of a wrong message. How to make it media-friendly? How to reach a network of journalists? How do we get our press release published? How to get on the political agenda? Need for communications training. Send correct messages, avoid hype but not boring. How to communicate when there is still no data?

Ideas: Using policy makers as communicators. Take into account the visual aspects (video, devices, people doing things...). Build and work on the story from the beginning: what the project brings, how it is innovative, what impact it has... Take advantage of current events or key moments to disseminate the project and not to do so when there is an information collapse. Connect with other projects. Spend time with certain journalists to establish a relationship. Mapping journalists and influencers of certain issues.

Challenges: Transmission of a wrong message, How to make it media-friendly? How to get a network of journalists? How do we get our press release published? How to get on the political agenda? Communications training. Send correct message, avoid hype but not boring. How to communicate when there is still no data?

Ideas: Using policy makers as communicators, Take into account the visual aspects (video, devices, people doing things...), Build and work on the story from the beginning: what the project brings, how it is innovative, what impact it has... To take advantage of current events or key moments to disseminate our project and not to do so when there is an information collapse. Connect with other projects. Spend time with certain journalists to establish a relationship. Mapping journalists

CS Practitioners group:

How can we use citizen generated data to produce attractive stories for journalists?

Picture 15. Example of the results of the first dynamic for the citizen science practitioners group at Adobe Spark: <https://spark.adobe.com/page/hJM6Vy23lvXMJ/>

Journalists group: Which is the main challenge that you face when you are working with (citizen generated) data?

Challenges: Origin & Validation of data. Mistakes. Time. Visual skills. Data overload. Political agenda. Independence of journalists. Voice. Is it a story? Bias. Representativeness. Design of data collection. Institutional activism. Lack of trust and feedback in the media. Need to understand the media process. Continuity & use of data.

Ideas: Enough time acquaintance to build trust, to have a public “agreement” on methodology & ethical frame. Detail feedback & Explicit methodology. Build knowledge on journalists' needs. Need of a third independent party to verify data reliability. Choose the right project. Citizens are “sources” and subjects as much as other players. More citizen journalism, less misinformation.

Picture 16. Members of the Journalists group showing their outcomes

Work Group 2: mixed groups

With the several issues and discussions between the two groups we try to find the common ground. With an open discussion with all the attendees, and taking advantage of the outcomes of the day before, we collected three common challenges and ideas about communication and citizen science projects as conclusions.

Challenges

1. Journalists and activists are not paid throughout the entire process.
2. Data validation (for career scientists and journalists)
3. Open data: how it was collected, which methodology was used, etc.

Ideas

1. Build together a strong collaboration, get to know each other, and set up concrete and common objectives.
2. Set up a collaboration agreement, both at individual (project) level and collective level (e.g. through your CS Network).
3. Training needs for journalists to better understand CS and for CS practitioners to understand journalism and media.

Summary of methodology contributions during co-creation sessions

Again, the second day was highly successful and participants were satisfied with the outcomes since it managed to generate a dialogue between two communities (citizen science practitioners and science communicators and journalists) that usually do not talk directly to each other. So this was a result in itself. The common challenges and ideas identified were relevant for both communities and an excellent starting point to initiate the work to be done in NEWSERA.

Regarding the methodologies used, the conclusions were as follows:

- Group discussion to detect needs and opportunities for the same type of stakeholder is enriching
- Not all stakeholders have the same scope and tools and it is necessary to take into account their day-to-day life work in order to get them involved
- An open debate looking for points of consensus is a good exercise to reach a common ground and conclusions

Picture 17. Group photo with partners and some participants in the co-creation sessions.

The open and shared report with the participative methods that we used in order to identify common challenges and ideas about science communication and citizen science projects is available at the following link:

<https://spark.adobe.com/page/hJM6Vy23lvXMJ/>

Picture 18. We used the Adobe Spark platform to provide feedback on the outcomes of the co-creation sessions to the participants

1.3 Kick-off meeting press clipping

- **13/02/2020.** NEWSERA: la ciencia ciudadana, una potente herramienta de comunicación

<https://www.heraldo.es/noticias/sociedad/2020/02/13/la-ciencia-ciudadana-una-potente-herramienta-de-comunicacion-1358409.html>

- **17/02/2020.** Arranca NEWSERA, el proyecto de comunicación científica ciudadana en el que participa FECYT

<https://www.fecyt.es/es/noticia/arranca-news-era-el-proyecto-de-comunicacion-cientifica-ciudadana-en-el-que-participa-fecyt>

- **Twitter report**

<https://wakelet.com/wake/f76832ae-b548-4363-9f75-15673af5d9ac>

Picture 19. Example of Twitter report by wakelet tool.

2. Planned events (M3 - M12)

Description and details of the meetings and events to be organised by the project consortium or to be attended by the NEWSERA partners from M3 to M12.

2.1 NEWSERA Consortium Meetings

The NEWSERA Consortium is organising monthly Executive Board meetings online, on the first Thursday of each month, to follow and agree on the project actions. The next face-to-face Consortium Meeting is planned to take place in Padova during the second week of December 2020.

However, the Consortium will strictly follow the recommendations of the European Commission and the indications of the governments of each country on the effects and mitigation strategies of the crisis of COVID-19. At the time of writing this report, the EC recommends not to travel at least until the end of June. This may not affect the celebration of the next face-to-face consortium meeting to be held in Padova, but in case that the situation does not allow to do this as planned, we will decide to hold it online or postpone it, according to the actual situation when the time comes.

For the time being, we also maintain the idea of holding the face-to-face consortium meetings at the same time as the #CitSciComm Labs, when travels will be allowed and safe again. If this can not be the case, our plan B is to hold the Consortium Meetings remotely and delocalised the functioning of the Labs, making them at the local level in the different partners' locations (i.e. Spain, Portugal and Italy).

Even so, and foreseeing a necessary reduction of the international trips of the external participants, we have thought it convenient to rethink the labs to reinforce the role of the local agents and to give the possibility of online co-creation between agents from several countries.

We expect to maintain other planned events as originally scheduled, but we are going to develop the better strategy case by case and according to the official recommendations, while promoting the collaboration between projects and avoiding overscheduling related events on close dates.

2.2 #CitSciComm Labs sessions

The NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs consist of 5 face-to-events and periodic remote meetings, as originally planned, to be executed across the project lifetime. Five #CitSciComm Labs will be created:

- 4 #CitSciComm Labs addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders (civil society, academia, policy makers, industry and SMEs)
- 1 cross-cutting #CitSciComm Lab addressed to science communicators and data journalists

Data journalists and communication experts will support the four #CitSciComm Labs to help citizen science practitioners to define innovative communication strategies within projects under execution to reach wider audiences.

The tentative calendar for the first year face-to-face events is the following:

- **Launch event of the #CitSciComm Labs:** June 2020 in Brussels (Belgium) - on hold at the moment
- **First encounter of the #CitSciComm Labs:** December 2020 in Padova (Italy), in parallel to the NEWSERA consortium meeting

We had considered to organize the #CitSciComm Labs at the same time as the NEWSERA Consortium Meetings (with the aim of optimizing travel costs and human resources).

The launch event of the Labs will definitely be affected by the COVID-19 crisis. According to the evolution of the situation, one possibility could be to do three national launch events in Spain, Italy and Portugal, probably around September or October 2020. A second possibility could be to maintain the location and organize the launch of the Labs in Brussels, in September or October 2020, if feasible. This will be decided when the level of uncertainty in travels is reduced once the COVID-19 crisis is over.

In addition, the consortium is looking for innovative ways of collaboration that can take place remotely and thus reduce the number of trips during, at least, the events to be organised during 2020. In any case, the members of the consortium are continuously in contact to take measures to reduce the impact of the COVID-19 crisis in the project.

Name of the event	Location	Planned date	Event type	Mitigation plan
#CitSciComm 1 (launch event)	Brussels	June 2020	First co-creation lab acting as launch event	It will likely be moved to September / October 2020 and: 1) delocalised (done in parallel in Spain, Italy and Portugal); 2) maintained in Brussels, if possible
#CitSciComm 2	Padova	December 2020	Second co-creation lab and also consortium meeting	Depending on the final date of celebration of the launch event, the data can be changed and the location can again be decentralised (Italy, Spain and Portugal), focused in local participants with remote participant options to allow for conversations between experts from different countries

Table 11. List of NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs affected by the COVID-19 crisis

2.3 External events

In the framework of the research being carried out within NEWSERA, several abstracts have been already accepted in scientific conferences, which were going to take place before summer 2020, but that have now been rescheduled due to the COVID-19 crisis. The most relevant one was the organization of a specific session for STS Italia by the consortium members (UNIPD, FECYT and Sfc) entitled “Responsible and inclusive citizen science. Comparing initiatives and assessing impacts”. For the session, to be chaired by the NEWSERA partners, up to eight abstracts have been accepted for oral presentations. We will be expecting the confirmations of the new dates so as to attend the foreseen events:

Name of the event	Location	Planned date	Status
8th SciComPT Congress	NONAGON, São Miguel, Lagoa, Azores.	May 7-8, 2020	Temporarily cancelled, waiting for a new date, probably in October 2020
ECSA Conference	Trieste	May 24-26, 2020	Rescheduled to September 6-8, 2020
II International Forum of Citizen Science in Spain	Madrid, Spain	June 17-19 2020	Postponed, we are waiting for a new date, probably in October 2020
VIII STS Italia Conference. Dis/Entangling Technoscience: vulnerability, responsibility and justice.	University of Trieste	June 18-20, 2020	Postponed, tentatively rescheduled for June 17-19, 2021

Table 11. List of external events related with NEWSERA affected by the COVID-19 crisis